

UNLOCKING DATA

Canada

GUIDANCE NOTE

DEVELOPING A RESEARCH AGENDA

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About the Unlocking Data Initiative

The Unlocking Data Initiative is a community of practice that connects African scholars, NGOs, national statistics offices, and policymakers to improve access to and use of education data. The **Unlocking Data: Scaling Uses and Users of Education Data** project is a collaborative effort led by Zizi Afrique Foundation and supported by Education Sub-Saharan Africa, eBase Africa, and the University of Malawi's Centre for Education Research and Training (CERT). The latter project, which is being implemented in Cameroon, Kenya and Malawi, aims to scale up the use and users of data to address the knowledge gap on how to adaptively scale up the effective use of existing education data by policymakers and researchers in Africa.

To learn more about us, visit <https://unlockingdata.africa/>. Our evidence library can be found at <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/>

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Abbreviations and acronyms

EGM	Evidence Gap Map
FL	Foundational learning
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
UDI	Unlocking Data Initiative

1. Introduction

This Guidance Note outlines the phases, steps, and strategies for developing a set of research priorities (agenda) to guide the next activities of the Unlocking Data Initiative (UDI). The UDI is a community of practice that brings together African scholars, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), national statistics offices, and policymakers to improve access to and use of education data. This initiative seeks to expand both the uses and the users of education data, with a focus on the foundational learning (FL) landscape for primary-school-age children across participating countries. To achieve these objectives, the UDI's approach relies on four main components:

1. Situational analyses at the country level with cross-country learning
2. Evidence Gap Maps (EGMs) and use of data to address priority questions
3. Cultivating communities of learning at the country and regional levels
4. Sharing and synthesising experiences and toolkits as global public goods

Following the situational analyses, which explore the strengths and challenges of the FL research landscape, and the EGMs, which probe for interventions and corresponding evidence, the UDI team now aims to identify which evidence gaps warrant urgent attention and to translate these gaps into a prioritised set of research questions.

This document details the entire process for identifying priority research questions that the UDI will consider in future research. Although there is no single blueprint for developing a research agenda, and the literature on the practical, step-by-step priority-setting process is limited, we recommend three phases, assuming the situational analyses and the EGMs have been conducted. These phases are:

The remainder of this document is organised as follows. [Section 2](#) describes the process for sharing the EGMs with education research stakeholders. [Section 3](#) elaborates on the co-creation workshops, and [Section 4](#) details the process for setting research priorities. [Section 5](#) concludes this guidance note.

2. Phase I: Presenting an EGM

This section discusses the relevance of an EGM and the key considerations for planning and conducting the co-creation workshops (Phase 2), with the aim of developing research priorities (Phase 3) to guide future research investments. As mentioned earlier, we assume that the team using this guidance note has completed background work, namely a situational analysis and an EGM. This phase treats an EGM as a facilitation and decision-support tool rather than solely a technical product.

2.1. Definition and relevance for co-creation workshops

Evidence Gap Maps (EGMs) are evidence synthesis tools that display the existing evidence on a specific topic and highlight gaps or areas of research scarcity. Hence, before engaging in a co-creation workshop that will drive the development of a set of research priorities, it is crucial to map and assess existing knowledge for evidence gaps (and the most covered thematic areas), as it helps set research priorities and guide evidence-based policymaking.

The implementation teams can conduct an EGM analysis and deliver interactive maps that can be updated annually (or on an agreed-upon cycle). UDI's reports discussing the EGMs for [Cameroon](#),¹ [Kenya](#)² and [Malawi](#)³ are available in the Unlocking Data Evidence Library. These analytic reports, namely [↑Arisa & Gachoki \(2025\)](#), [↑Pambe et al. \(2025\)](#) and [↑Saddick et al. \(2025\)](#), are crucial information resources for FL data and evidence producers (and users) and serve as material for co-creation workshops.

EGM technical reports and accompanying documentation (e.g., the coding framework, inclusion / exclusion criteria, and search strategy) should be made available to workshop participants in advance, where appropriate. These materials support evidence producers and users by clarifying what is and is not covered in a map, and how EGMs should be interpreted for priority setting.

¹ Available online:

https://unlockingdata.africa/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/cameroon_EGM_on-_foundational_learning.html [Last accessed 6 February 2026].

² Available online:https://unlockingdata.africa/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/EGM_Kenya.html [Last accessed 6 February 2026].

³ Available

online:<https://unlockingdata.africa/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Malawi-EGM-on-FLN.html> [Last accessed 6 February 2026].

2.2. Presenting and leveraging an EGM for co-creation

To present and leverage an EGM for co-creation with stakeholders, including government officials, educators, education researchers and funders, we suggest adopting the three important considerations or steps below:

Figure 1. *Three considerations or steps for presenting an EGM*

Step I: Walk the audience through the map

Purpose: This is to briefly and simply explain what an EGM is, describing it as a tool highlighting existing and missing evidence on a specific topic, in this case, FL. At this point, you can also describe the process of developing the scientific evidence map, including the sources of information (studies) and the coding framework used. Once participants understand the objective, you can explain how your EGM is organised and how to interpret it. EGMs can be displayed in different formats (e.g., a matrix, bubble chart, or other visual / interactive layouts), but the aim is the same: to help users see where evidence is concentrated and where gaps remain, and where applicable, how the map conveys both the volume and quality of evidence.

Note: It is useful to provide concrete examples during this presentation, for example, highlighting areas where the evidence is strong for interventions and where research is limited.

Takeaways: Highlights the rigour of the process and its relevance to policy and practice. The map's purpose extends beyond research: it helps identify priority areas for action.

Step II: Make the EGM presentation interactive

Purpose: It is crucial to make an EGM session interactive because its value lies in collective engagement. In so doing, we suggest encouraging stakeholders to question the EGM and reflect on its contextual impact on knowledge generation and use. This can be achieved through guided discussions, asking questions such as 'Where do you see strong evidence that could be immediately used for policy or practice?' or 'Which gaps are most critical to your work as researchers, decision-makers or FL practitioners?' Small group discussions can be used to gather stakeholders' perspectives and ensure that all voices are considered.

Note: Avoid presenting an EGM as a finished product.

Takeaways: An EGM is not a finished product. It needs regular updates to include new research outputs.

Step III: Link the evidence gaps to decision-making

Purpose: To conclude the discussions, it is essential to link an EGM to decision-making by translating its main results or findings into practical implications for policy, practices, research and funding. For example:

- i. Highlight how existing evidence in some areas can be considered (and re-assessed or synthesised, if needed) to improve interventions.
- ii. Gaps in other areas are opportunities for new research or collaboration.

Note: In doing so, an EGM is not an academic exercise, but a tool for setting important priorities for governments, donors, and practitioners.

Takeaways: Stakeholder groups have different perspectives on the implications of EGMs.

Guiding stakeholders through these three steps will help them understand the rigour of the EGM creation process and its relevance for policy and practice. It also makes clear that a map's purpose extends beyond research, as it helps identify priority action areas. Moreover, it emphasises that an EGM is not a static product but requires regular updates to incorporate new research outputs. Finally, this process ensures that different stakeholder groups develop and articulate their perspectives on an EGM's implications, which can then be shared during a co-creation session.

3. Phase II: The co-creation session

3.1. Stakeholders' selection

Co-creation sessions form a central element in the research agenda development process, facilitating inclusive stakeholder engagement and consensus-building. However, while an EGM presentation (Phase 1) targets a wide range of stakeholders, the co-creation component may require only a subset of workshop participants, often around 20–25 participants (or a size that remains manageable for facilitated group work).

We recommend selecting from the following categories, each of which plays a different role in the co-creation process and helps ensure that the resulting priorities are both technically robust and decision-relevant.

Stakeholder group	Assigned / Expected role
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Researchers	Provide technical expertise on existing evidence, methodologies, and analytical feasibility. Identify methodological gaps, assess the robustness of existing studies, and translate this into well-formulated research questions. Support refinement and prioritisation of questions to ensure academic rigour and policy relevance.
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Education practitioners, educators, and professional associations	Bring grounded, practice-based and professional perspectives on educational challenges. Validate whether the EGM reflects classroom realities and system-wide constraints. Support the formulation of research questions related to pedagogy, teacher preparation, continuous professional development, assessment practices, and the feasibility of reforms from implementation and professional practice standpoints.
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Policymakers	Articulate policy priorities, information needs, and decision-making constraints. Assess the relevance of proposed research questions to national and sub-national education strategies, reforms, and accountability frameworks. Ensure that prioritised questions have clear pathways to policy uptake and use (e.g., alignment with planning and budgeting cycles).
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Funders of education research	Provide insights into funders' priorities and investment considerations. Assess the feasibility and scalability of the proposed research questions, and identify opportunities to align with funding windows. Support prioritisation based on potential impact and sustainability (including prospects for follow-up funding and learning agendas).
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Stakeholder group	Assigned / Expected role
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Civil society organisations and NGOs	Share community-level perspectives and equity concerns, particularly for marginalised / vulnerable groups. Highlight implementation gaps, contextual barriers, and unintended consequences of interventions. Contribute to ensuring that research priorities address inclusion and social justice aspects of education and remain accountable to learners and communities.
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National statistics offices and data producers	Advise on data availability and quality, access, and opportunities for data linkage. Assess the feasibility of the proposed research questions given existing assessment data. Support alignment between research priorities and national data infrastructures, and clarify early practical access / data governance constraints.
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Others (e.g. parent associations, community representatives, youth organisations)	Offer user and beneficiary perspectives on foundational learning outcomes and service delivery. Help ground research priorities in lived experiences and community expectations, particularly regarding access, quality, and relevance of education (including acceptability and unintended harms)
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Finally, the selection must be guided by the need to ensure balanced representation of diverse stakeholders, genders, geographic contexts, and lived experiences. Participants should include both decision-makers and those directly involved in implementation to ensure that strategic and operational perspectives are considered. At the same time, the group must remain small enough to enable inclusive, targeted, and constructive deliberations.

3.2. Formation of thematic groups

Purpose: The formation of thematic groups has two main objectives: i. identify existing challenges and persistent evidence gaps within their thematic domain; ii. articulate research questions that directly address these gaps. This ensures that research priorities are grounded in the complexity and real-world implementation challenges.

Group formation: We recommend organising selected participants into groups around key thematic areas, including pedagogy and teaching practices; language of instruction; assessment and learning outcomes; teacher preparation and continuous professional development; and equity and inclusion.

Moreover, to ensure deliberation, we recommend selecting participants from the stakeholder categories above and assigning them to thematic groups based on their demonstrated expertise and areas of professional experience. In doing so, it is crucial to

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ensure equity and inclusivity while maintaining heterogeneity. Hence, within each group, facilitators should ensure a mix of stakeholder types so that no group is composed solely of researchers, practitioners, or policymakers.

This design deliberately integrates technical expertise, practical insight, and policy perspectives within a single thematic discussion. The facilitation team leads this allocation process before (or at the start of) the session and clearly explains the rationale to participants to support transparency. Each group appoints a rapporteur and a facilitator and utilises an established template to record the questions and rationale.

For example, a researcher working on instruction, teaching methodologies, or instructional coaching can be assigned to the pedagogy and teaching practices thematic group, while a policymaker responsible for teacher management or professional development may be allocated to the teacher preparation and professional development group. Similarly, education practitioners with experience in multilingual classrooms may be assigned to the language-of-instruction group. Similarly, civil society actors working with marginalised learners can make a significant contribution to the equity and inclusion group.

3.3. Facilitating activities

Group facilitation requires participatory approaches to surface diverse perspectives and foster genuine co-creation. Facilitators guide participants through a structured brainstorming process to ensure consistency and clarity in question formulation, while allowing space for contextualised dialogue and productive disagreement.

We encourage facilitators to use techniques such as gallery walks, in which groups present their emerging research questions for peer review, and small-group rotations to enable cross-pollination of ideas and the iterative refinement of priorities. This design, integrating structure and flexibility, explicitly values the expertise of practitioners, policymakers, and researchers alike, ensuring that the resulting research questions are not merely academically rigorous but also practically relevant and responsive to diverse stakeholders' information needs. A simple way to strengthen outputs is to require each group to document: (i) the draft questions, (ii) the gap it addresses, (iii) why the research matters, and (iv) what data / methods might be feasible, without locking in a single study design too early.

4. Phase III: Developing research priorities

Upon completing the co-creation session, facilitators proceed to the formal development and prioritisation of research questions (Phase III) to ensure that selected priorities are both relevant and actionable.

This final phase comprises three main steps: reviewing group activities, ranking research priorities, and conducting a peer review or adopting priority themes. This phase benefits most from a simple rubric and clear documentation.

Activities	Rationale
Step 1: Review of the groups' thematic and priority questions	<p>All proposed questions resulting from thematic group work are reviewed in a plenary discussion, where participants merge, refine, and validate research topics.</p> <p>At this step, facilitators can display all suggested research themes or questions on a board to ease the review process. Next, guided by participants' suggestions, similar topics are reviewed and systematically grouped (e.g., by theme, intervention, outcome, or data source).</p>
Step 2: Ranking of research priorities	<p>Criteria for prioritisation include alignment with sector priorities, urgency and timeliness, feasibility given available data and resources, equity and inclusion considerations, and potential impact on policy and programmes.</p> <p>Groups use a scoring system to rate research questions by importance across these dimensions. Clarity improves if facilitators specify the scoring scale in advance (e.g., 1–5), define what 'high' and 'low' mean for each criterion, and record brief justifications for the top-ranked items.</p>
Step 3: Adoption of priority themes	<p>The resulting list of top-priority questions, typically six to eight, is agreed upon through consensus, representing the diverse interests and evidence needs of all participants. When consensus is difficult to reach, prioritise a small set of near-term priorities rather than forcing agreement.</p>

Following the prioritisation activities, an implementation roadmap is established, allocating groups to specific research tasks, setting milestones and timelines, and scheduling regular meetings to monitor progress. Interlinking evidence needs and stakeholder perspectives ensures that the process cultivates a shared research agenda that is both robust and responsive to the pressing challenges facing foundational learning across participating contexts.

5. Conclusion

This document outlines the complete process for creating a research agenda, building on UDI's previous work. The Initiative has laid the groundwork by proposing situational analyses of the foundational learning landscape in the three selected countries and evidence gap maps, which are crucial to the creation of the research agenda. Together, these tools help identify priority evidence needs and structure a transparent pathway from 'what is known' to 'what should be studied next'.

Three main phases are foundational to creating a research agenda. These are:

- Presenting the emerging evidence or knowledge gaps to stakeholders (i.e., relevant evidence, producers, and users);
- Organising a co-creation session with all or a subgroup of stakeholders who participated in the dissemination phase (Phase I);
- Developing a consolidated list of research priorities through transparent prioritisation criteria and documented decision-making.

Each phase includes several recommended steps to enhance the co-creation process. Finally, we recommend that the facilitation team be creative, anticipatory, and imaginative in adapting the process to the context while maintaining methodological consistency and clear documentation of how practices were selected.

References

These references are available digitally in our evidence library at

<https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/75XAMDRE>

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